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SCREENS AND EDUCATION: THE USE OF ELECTRONIC MEDIA BY CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the various aspects related to the use of screens, such as smartphones, tablets and computers, as a pedagogical tool by children and adolescents. It examines the potential impacts on physical and mental health, as well as on social and academic skills. It also considers strategies for a balanced and healthy use of screens, aiming to promote holistic development in the crucial stages of childhood and adolescence in teaching and learning.